

MOLECULAR DELINEATION OF *DRYOPTERIS* SPECIES USING PLASTID DNA BARCODES: AN *IN-SILICO* COMPUTATIONAL ANALYSISStalin Nithaniyal^{1*} and Jesubalan D¹¹Botanical Survey of India (BSI),

Western Regional Centre (WRC), Koregaon Road, Pune, Maharashtra, 411001, India.

nstalin@bsi.gov.in

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Abstract

Morphology-based taxonomy was extensively used to distinguish *Dryopteris* species. However, resolving species complex is still problematic using existing methods. The current study employed DNA barcoding to validate the effectiveness of plastid DNA barcode markers, specifically using the coding regions *rbcl*, *matK*, *psbA*, and *atpB* loci, among the twelve *Dryopteris* species to resolve the complexity. Computational approaches were used to annotate, analyse, and calculate the DNA sequence composition of each DNA marker using different parameters. The results indicated that the nucleotide variability was high in *matK* and *atpB* which increases the resolving power among *Dryopteris* species. The *psbA* and *rbcl* markers showed low differentiation and were not suitable for distinguishing species. The phylogenetic tree was constructed using the maximum-likelihood method to understand the genetic relationship among the twelve *Dryopteris* species. The gene tree constructed using *matK* and *atpB* DNA barcodes resolved all the twelve species, such as *D. championii*, *D. crassirhizoma*, *D. decipiens*, *D. deparioides*, *D. filix-mas*, *D. fragrans*, *D. fulgens*, *D. gaoligongensis*, *D. goeringiana*, *D. podophylla*, *D. sieboldii*, *D. sinonepalensis*, *D. sparsa*, and *D. yorii*. In contrast, the *psbA* and *rbcl* locus demonstrated less efficacy in differentiating the species. The resolving power was significantly enhanced when using the *matK* and *atpB* markers making it a more suitable DNA barcode for assessing genetic relatedness *Dryopteris* at the species level. This comprehensive study provides the valuable insights on selection of appropriate DNA barcode loci for species authentication and understanding the phylogenetic relationships within the Polypodiaceae.

Keywords: *Dryopteris*, Polypodiaceae, DNA barcode, *matK*, *rbcl*, *psbA*, *atpB*, Chloroplast markers

Introduction

The wood fern genus *Dryopteris* Adans. is a cosmopolitan form of the family Polypodiaceae and occurs in the tropical, temperate, and boreal regions and on many oceanic islands. The center of diversity is primarily lies in southern and eastern Asia with a diverse set of habitats, morphologies, and hybridization events and polyploidy appears to be common. There are about 208 species recognized and classified in four subgenera and 16 sections. Morphological identification of *Dryopteris* is difficult, and several species complexes were not resolved because of look-alike species, hybrids, and unresolved nomenclature (Sessa *et al.* 2012). Rapid species identification is crucial for the conservation of endemic and threatened species of *Dryopteris*. However, it is highly challenging and often lacks distinct morphological character to distinguish closely related species. DNA barcode-based species identification could overcome these limitations and recently emerged as a powerful tool to delineate and classify Pteridophytes. DNA barcoding utilizes a short, standardized DNA fragment to identify species. This method is adopted worldwide as a rapid and reliable identification method for distinguishing closely related species (Hebert *et al.* 2003). The chloroplast DNA regions *rbcl*, *matK*, *psbA* and *atpB* are used as barcoding markers to identify Pteridophytes since they show relatively high sequence conservation and universality (CBOL, 2009). Various studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of DNA barcoding markers in resolving complex genus with high-quality sequences for species-level identification across diverse Pteridophytes taxa (Ebihara *et al.* 2010; Wang *et al.* 2016). However, the degree of resolution in different taxonomic groups could vary in terms of the effectiveness of markers, and their ability to resolve species within the *Dryopteris* genus is not established completely. The present study focused on a comprehensive computational validation of the chloroplast genome markers *rbcl*, *matK*, *psbA* and *atpB* in the *Dryopteris* genus. The study seeks to assess their efficacy in species identification and phylogenetic resolution within *Dryopteris*. The study revealed valuable insights on the phylogenetic relationships among *Dryopteris* species. Furthermore, this study will provide a broader application of DNA barcoding in *Dryopteris* identification, classification, authentication and conservation of species within the Polypodiaceae.

Materials and Methods**Dataset of *Dryopteris* species**

The DNA sequences of *rbcl*, *matK*, *psbA*, and *atpB* for fourteen *Dryopteris* species belonging to Polypodiaceae were downloaded from the chloroplast genome using the NCBI nucleotide database

(<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>). The sequences of each species were retrieved from the corresponding region in the chloroplast genome. The details of *Dryopteris* fourteen species and their GenBank accession number are *D. championii* (OR601539), *D. crassirhizoma* (MN712465), *D. decipiens* (KY427348), *D. deparioides* (MW796571), *D. filix-mas* (AB089917), *D. fragrans* (KX418656.2), *D. fulgens* (MW796572), *D. gaoligongensis* (MW796575), *D. goeringiana* (MN712463), *D. podophylla* (OR601540), *D. sieboldii* (MN623354), *D. sinonepalensis* (MW796576), *D. sparsa* (MW796574), and *D. yorii* (MW796579).

Validation and Curation of DNA barcode sequences

The GenBank database of NCBI was searched for the presence of *Dryopteris* DNA barcode sequences. The DNA barcode sequences were validated and curated based on the following criteria suggested in previous studies (Sivaraj *et al.* 2018; Yadav *et al.* 2024) such as i) the data was tagged with publication in refereed journals or unpublished data from scientists with good publication record in taxonomy, ii) placed in a clade that is appropriate to its taxonomic affiliation, and iii) showed proper sequence alignment using MUSCLE algorithm (Edgar 2004) with 70% threshold.

Computational analysis of DNA barcoding markers

The DNA sequences of all the species were saved in FASTA format for analysis. The nucleotide composition and the average size were calculated. The sequences were annotated in Multiple Sequence Alignment by ClustalW using MEGA 11 software (Tamura *et al.* 2024). Evolutionary divergence for each dataset and pattern of nucleotide substitution was performed by the same software. The phylogenetic analysis was carried out using the maximum likelihood tree method with 1000 bootstrap confidence. In order to estimate species resolution in four DNA barcode loci, we considered individuals formed monophyletic clade in the phylogenetic tree with high bootstrap support value.

Results and Discussion**Genetic divergence analysis of *Dryopteris***

The sequence divergences were estimated using pairwise combinations formed by the fourteen species of *Dryopteris*. The sequence length of DNA barcodes of *rbcl*, *matK*, *psbA*, and *atpB* were 1428 bp, 1507 bp, 1062 bp, and 1482 bp, respectively. Size variation was not observed between species for any of the sequences in all four DNA markers studied. The genetic distance was calculated individually for each DNA barcode marker by estimating the nucleotide variability. The genetic distances in the *rbcl*, *matK*, *psbA*, and *atpB* regions were found to be 0.00-0.04, 0.00-0.08, 0.00-0.01, and 0.00-0.03, respectively

(Tables 1, 2, 3 and 4). Results from our analysis showed that the *matK* DNA barcodes of *D. deparioides*, *D. fragrans*, *D. fulgens*, *D. fulgens*, *D. fulgens*, *D. gaoligongensis*, *D. podophylla*, and *D. sparsa* displayed the highest divergence with maximum p-distance of 0.08. This was followed by the *rbcL* DNA barcode region of *D. fragrans*, *D. deparioides* with maximum p-distance of 0.04 and the *atpB* DNA barcode regions from the *D. deparioides*, *D. fragrans*, *D. fulgens*, *D. gaoligongensis*, *D. goeringiana*, *D. podophylla*, *D. sinonepalensis*, and *D. sparsa* showed maximum p-distance of 0.03 than the other

Dryopteris species. In the case of *psbA* region, all of the *Dryopteris* species showed the lowest divergence, ranging from 0.00 to 0.01, indicating less efficacy to be used as DNA barcoding marker. This finding aligns with a previous study, which demonstrated that the *matK* region had significantly higher identification efficiency (Sun *et al.* 2012; Wang *et al.* 2016; Liu *et al.* 2016). Moreover, recent reported low discrimination efficiency of *psbA* (Sen *et al.* 2012; Cabelin *et al.* 2016).

Table 1: Estimation of evolutionary divergence in *rbcL* sequence between species pairs of *Dryopteris*

	Species Name	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
1	<i>D. championii</i>	0													
2	<i>D. crassirhizoma</i>	0.03	0												
3	<i>D. decipiens</i>	0.00	0.03	0											
4	<i>D. deparioides</i>	0.03	0.03	0.03	0										
5	<i>D. filix-mas</i>	0.03	0.01	0.03	0.03	0									
6	<i>D. fragrans</i>	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.03	0								
7	<i>D. fulgens</i>	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.03	0							
8	<i>D. gaoligongensis</i>	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.01	0						
9	<i>D. goeringiana</i>	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.03	0					
10	<i>D. podophylla</i>	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.02	0				
11	<i>D. sieboldii</i>	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.03	0			
12	<i>D. sinonepalensis</i>	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.02	0.03	0		
13	<i>D. sparsa</i>	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.01	0	
14	<i>D. yoroii</i>	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.02	0

Table 2: Estimation of evolutionary divergence in *matK* sequence between species pairs of *Dryopteris*

	Species Name	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
1	<i>D. championii</i>	0													
2	<i>D. crassirhizoma</i>	0.07	0												
3	<i>D. decipiens</i>	0.00	0.06	0											
4	<i>D. deparioides</i>	0.08	0.07	0.07	0										
5	<i>D. filix-mas</i>	0.05	0.02	0.06	0.07	0									
6	<i>D. fragrans</i>	0.07	0.06	0.07	0.08	0.05	0								
7	<i>D. fulgens</i>	0.08	0.06	0.08	0.03	0.06	0.08	0							
8	<i>D. gaoligongensis</i>	0.08	0.06	0.07	0.02	0.06	0.07	0.02	0						
9	<i>D. goeringiana</i>	0.06	0.02	0.06	0.07	0.01	0.06	0.06	0.06	0					
10	<i>D. podophylla</i>	0.02	0.07	0.02	0.07	0.06	0.07	0.08	0.07	0.06	0				
11	<i>D. sieboldii</i>	0.07	0.02	0.07	0.07	0.02	0.06	0.07	0.06	0.02	0.07	0			
12	<i>D. sinonepalensis</i>	0.07	0.06	0.06	0.02	0.05	0.07	0.02	0.01	0.05	0.07	0.06	0		
13	<i>D. sparsa</i>	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.02	0.06	0.08	0.03	0.02	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.02	0	
14	<i>D. yoroii</i>	0.06	0.05	0.06	0.03	0.05	0.06	0.03	0.03	0.05	0.06	0.05	0.02	0.03	0

Table 3: Estimation of evolutionary divergence *psbA* sequence between species pairs of *Dryopteris*

	Species Name	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
1	<i>D. championii</i>	0													
2	<i>D. crassirhizoma</i>	0.01	0												
3	<i>D. decipiens</i>	0.00	0.01	0											
4	<i>D. deparioides</i>	0.01	0.01	0.01	0										
5	<i>D. filix-mas</i>	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00	0									
6	<i>D. fragrans</i>	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0								
7	<i>D. fulgens</i>	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00	0							
8	<i>D. gaoligongensis</i>	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0						
9	<i>D. goeringiana</i>	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0					
10	<i>D. podophylla</i>	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0				
11	<i>D. sieboldii</i>	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0			
12	<i>D. sinonepalensis</i>	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0		
13	<i>D. sparsa</i>	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0	

14	<i>D. yoroii</i>	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0
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Table 4: Estimation of evolutionary divergence *atpB* sequence between species pairs of *Dryopteris*

	Species Name	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
1	<i>D. championii</i>	0													
2	<i>D. crassirhizoma</i>	0.02	0												
3	<i>D. decipiens</i>	0.00	0.02	0											
4	<i>D. deparioides</i>	0.02	0.02	0.03	0										
5	<i>D. filix-mas</i>	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.02	0									
6	<i>D. fragrans</i>	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0								
7	<i>D. fulgens</i>	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.03	0							
8	<i>D. gaoligongensis</i>	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.01	0						
9	<i>D. goeringiana</i>	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.03	0.02	0.02	0					
10	<i>D. podophylla</i>	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0				
11	<i>D. sieboldii</i>	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.02	0			
12	<i>D. sinonepalensis</i>	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.02	0		
13	<i>D. sparsa</i>	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.01	0	
14	<i>D. yoroii</i>	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0

Phylogenetic Analysis and evolutionary relationship within *Dryopteris*

The efficacy of DNA barcode was determined by its ability to delineate the closely related taxa and to provide species level identification based on interspecific divergences. In this study, the species are considered resolved when the individual sequences form a monophyletic clade. Using this criterion, three out of the fourteen species, *D. championii*, *D. decipiens*, and *D. podophylla*, were not resolved by the *psbA* and *rbcL* region (Figures 1 and 3). However, all the species were resolved using *matK* and *atpB* DNA barcodes. For clarity, Phylogenetic tree with high bootstrap values >80% are shown above the branches (Figures 2 and 4). The topology of phylogenetic trees constructed using all the DNA barcode markers were similar except *rbcL* marker. The DNA barcode regions of *matK* and *atpB* exhibited a high level of discrimination. In this study, neither *rbcL* nor *psbA* could not discriminate all species but, the *matK* and *atpB* sequence discriminated

all species in the phylogenetic analysis, and the results were presented in Figure 1, 2,3,4. The phylogenetic tree of *matK* and *atpB* sequences resolved fourteen species such as *D. championii*, *D. crassirhizoma*, *D. decipiens*, *D. deparioides*, *D. filix-mas*, *D. fragrans*, *D. fulgens*, *D. gaoligongensis*, *D. goeringiana*, *D. podophylla*, *D. sieboldii*, *D. sinonepalensis*, *D. sparsa*, and *D. yoroii* in three distinct clades. Several studies, including those on *Hibiscus* (Poovitha *et al.* 2016), *Fabaceae* (Gao *et al.* 2010), and TDEF flora (Nithaniyal *et al.* 2014), have reported the high capacity of the *matK* and *atpB* DNA barcode region in plant identification. However, its discrimination efficiency may be lower in some cases, such as with tropical tree species. The effectiveness of using *rbcL*, and *psbA*, alone for plant species discrimination is limited and, in such case, *matK* and *atpB* DNA barcode along with nuclear marker like ITS2 could be employed for unambiguous identification (Yao *et al.* 2010).

Figure 1. Maximum Likelihood tree of *rbcL* DNA barcode for *Dryopteris*. Numbers above branches denotes the bootstrap values.

Figure 2. Maximum Likelihood tree of *matK* DNA barcode for *Dryopteris*. Numbers above branches denotes the bootstrap values.

Figure 3. Maximum Likelihood tree of *psbA* DNA barcode for *Dryopteris*. Numbers above branches denotes the bootstrap values.

Figure 4. Maximum Likelihood tree of *atpB* DNA barcode for *Dryopteris*. Numbers above branches denotes the bootstrap values.

Conclusion

The results of this study suggest that the species-resolving ability of the *rbcL*, *matK*, *psbA*, and *atpB* regions varied among different *Dryopteris* species. The coding region *matK* and *atpB* DNA barcodes significantly enhance species discrimination. However, the *psbA* marker is limited by nucleotide variability of sequences that could not be suitable for species identification. This comparative study of chloroplast genome indicates the ability of coding region as potential DNA barcode marker among the chloroplast genes and to delineate *Dryopteris* species. The current study reinforces the use of *matK* and

atpB DNA barcodes as the best maker for molecular identification of *Dryopteris* based on the universality, nucleotide variability, and phylogenetic resolution within the family Polypodiaceae.

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to this article.

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